

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**
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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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CLINICAL COURSE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH PRE-EXISTING CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES**Oblokulov A.R.¹, Shodmonov I.S.²**¹Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Bukhara, Uzbekistan²Turon University, Karshi, Uzbekistan

Resume. Specific immunological indicators and changes in the level of inflammatory cytokines in patients with pathology of the cardiovascular system are based on the calculation of reliable primary preventive predictors for the development of severe Covid-19 infection, "cytokin storm" and cardiovascular complications (myocarditis, acute coronary syndrome). Also, the fact that the ratio of these immunological markers is a criterion that predicts the level of clinical severity and negative consequences of comorbid disease (concomitant course of coronavirus and cardiac pathology) in patients is presented through the results of a medical study.

Keywords: COVID-19, cardiovascular diseases, clinical course, complications, prognosis.

ЮРАК-ҚОН ТОМИР КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ МАВЖУД БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА COVID-19 НИНГ КЛИНИК КЕЧИШИ**Облокулов А.Р.¹, Шодмонов И.С.²**¹Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон²Турон университети, Қарши ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Юрак-қон томир тизими патологиясига чалинган беморларда ўзига хос иммунологик кўрсаткичлар ва яллигланиш цитокинлари даражасининг ўзгариши COVID-19 инфекциясининг оғир кечиши, "цитокин бўрони" ҳамда кардиоваскуляр асоратлар (миокардит, ўткир коронар синдром) ривожланишининг ишончли бирламчи профилактика предикторлари ҳисобланиши асослаб берилган. Шунингдек, ушбу иммунологик маркерларнинг ўзаро нисбати беморларда коморбид касалликнинг (коронавирус ва юрак патологияси биргаликда кечишининг) клиник оғирлик даражасини ва салбий оқибатларни олдиндан кўрсатиб берувчи мезон эканлиги тиббий тадқиқот натижалари орқали келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: COVID-19, юрак-қон томир касалликлари, клиник кечиши, асоратлар, прогноз.

КЛИНИЧЕСКОЕ ТЕЧЕНИЕ COVID-19 У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ПРЕДСУЩЕСТВУЮЩИМИ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ**Облокулов А.Р.¹, Шодмонов И.С.²**¹Бухарский государственный медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино, г. Бухара, Узбекистан²Турон Университет, г. Карши, Узбекистан

Резюме. Специфические иммунологические показатели и изменения уровня воспалительных цитокинов у пациентов с патологией сердечно-сосудистой системы основаны на расчете надежных первичных профилактических предикторов развития тяжелой инфекции Covid-19, "цитокинового шторма" и сердечно-сосудистых осложнений (миокардит, острый коронарный синдром). Также тот факт, что соотношение этих иммунологических маркеров является критерием, который предсказывает уровень клинической тяжести и негативные последствия сопутствующего заболевания (сопутствующее течение коронавируса и кардиальной патологии) у пациентов, представлен результатами медицинского исследования.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, клиническое течение, осложнения, прогноз.

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Introduction. In recent years, COVID-19 coronavirus infection has emerged as a serious threat to public health globally [1]. It is characterized by its course as a multi-organ pathological process that covers not only the respiratory system, but also the cardiovascular, nervous, endocrine and immune systems [2]. The declaration of a new coronavirus infection as a pandemic by the WHO on 11 March 2020 further increased the medico-social importance of this disease [3].

According to epidemiological data, the severe and severe course of COVID-19 infection is often associated with the size of the age and the presence of companion diseases, in particular cardiovascular diseases. Cardiovascular pathologies such as Arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, heart failure, arrhythmias and atherosclerosis are characterized by high mortality rates and an unfavorable clinical prognosis in patients with COVID-19 [4-6].

The effects of SARS-CoV-2 virus on the cardiovascular system are mediated by a number of pathogenic mechanisms. The entry of the virus into endothelium and cardiomyocytes through ACE2 receptors leads to the development of a systemic inflammatory response and "cytokine storm", a state of hypercoagulation and microcirculation disorders, myocardial damage and thrombotic complications [7]. This in turn increases the risk of severe COVID-19 and lethal outcomes.

The development of measures aimed at identifying and eliminating diseases that develop multi-organ inflammatory processes in patients with COVID-19 around the world, as well as risk factors that lead to their occurrence, is one of the most pressing medical and economic problems of modern infectology [8].

However, clinical practice shows that in patients with cardiovascular diseases, COVID-19 is characterized by the preservation of cardiovascular complications or the occurrence of new forms, not only in the acute period, but also at the stage of convalescence. This situation necessitates the need for long-term follow-up and comprehensive rehabilitation of these patients [9].

Since the emergence of COVID-19, many scientific studies devoted to its clinical course, pathogenesis and complications have been conducted on a global scale. In particular, in patients with cardiovascular disease, the rejection characteristics of COVID-19 infection are of particular interest in clinical medicine [10].

Identifying comorbidities that promote multi-organ inflammatory processes in patients with COVID-19 worldwide, as well as the factors contributing to their development, and developing measures to counteract them are considered some of the most pressing medical and economic problems in modern infectology [11]. At the same time, clinical practice shows that in patients with cardiovascular diseases, the effects of COVID-19 on the cardiovascular system persist not only during the acute phase but also in the convalescence period, with the maintenance of cardiovascular effects or the emergence of new forms [12]. This situation necessitates long-term monitoring and comprehensive rehabilitation for these patients.

Materials and Methods. This study is a single-center retrospective cohort study, which we selected from all patients with confirmed COVID-19 infection who were admitted to the regional infectious diseases hospital in qarshi from March 21 to December 31, 2020. Clinical data was obtained from electronic medical cards, including demographic data, medical history, signs and symptoms, and laboratory data at the time of admission. Typical blood analyses were: leukocyte count (WBC), lymphocyte count (LYM), mononuclear count (MONO), neutrophil count (NEU), platelet blood samples. Parameters of blood biochemistry: aspartataminotransferase (ast), alaninaminotransferase (Alt), glucose (GLU), mochevina, creatinine, and C-reactive protein (SRO) were measured using the MINDRAY BS – 30 (China) automatic biochemical analyzer. Coagulation functions (prothrombin time (PTV), fibrinogen (FIB), activated partial thromboplastin time (FQPV) were determined using the Mindray BA – 88A (China) analyzer. The concentration of the D-dimer was determined using sets of reagents using the IFT method. D-dimer-IFA - BEST reagents were used to determine the concentration of D-dimer in blood plasma. The concentration of antibodies to phospholipids was determined using the IgM/IgG ift method. For the data of patients of moderate to severe levels, their results in the first laboratory test at the time of admission were used. All analysis was carried out by specially appointed personnel, strictly following the instructions for the use of reagents.

Results. The results of clinical observation show that patients who have been diagnosed with COVID-19 coronavirus infection have a high comorbidity rate of prevalence of pathologies of the cardiovascular system. When the comorbid background in the study group was analyzed, the highest was found to be the contribution of arterial hypertension (AG), with 93.4% of patients having this nosology. This indicator serves as the main factor that further aggravates the course of coronavirus infection in the context of systemic vasoconstriction and endothelial dysfunction (Table 1).

Table 1.

The proportion of cardiovascular pathologies studied in patients

№	Name of existing cardiovascular disease	Percentage compared to the number of patients, in %
1.	Arterial hypertension	93,4 %
2.	Chronic heart failure	60,9 %
3.	Cardiac arrhythmias (arrhythmias)	40,1 %
4.	Ischemic heart disease	21,9 %

In the structural structure, chronic decompensation processes occupy the next places; in particular, 60.9% of patients have chronic heart failure and 40.1% have different manifestations of cardiac arrhythmias (arrhythmias). Direct and indirect (hypoxic, cytokine) damage to the myocardium caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus increases the risk of acute heart failure several times against the background of these pathologies.

The lowest was in the proportion of ischemic heart disease in 21.9% of patients.

The results obtained indicate that AG and Sue occupy a leading position in the structure of cardiovascular comorbidity in patients with COVID-19. This ensures that in the process of treating patients of this contingent, not only anti-viral and anti-inflammatory therapy, but also cardioprotective and antihypertensive treatment measures are prematurely and purposefully directed.

The figure below shows information on the structure of hypertension by strain (Figure 1).

Fig. 1

An analysis of the structure of comorbid cardiovascular pathologies showed that a Level 3 AG priority for the severity of arterial hypertension among observable patients was recorded in 66.5% of cases. This phenomenon is evidenced by the high risk of target limb destruction and systemic hemodynamic disturbances in the comorbid contingent.

Conclusion. The findings of this study indicate that pre-existing cardiovascular diseases significantly worsen the clinical course and outcomes of COVID-19. Patients with cardiovascular comorbidities are more likely to develop severe forms of the disease, experience cardiovascular and thromboembolic complications, require intensive care, and have higher in-hospital mortality rates compared to patients without cardiovascular pathology.

Cardiovascular diseases should be considered an independent predictor of poor prognosis in patients with COVID-19. Early risk stratification, careful cardiovascular monitoring, and timely multidisciplinary management are essential to reduce complications and improve clinical outcomes in this high-risk population.

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